

THE PROBLEM OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article points to the role of the Russian language in the world, the need to promote it in the countries of near and far abroad and improve the quality of its study in the Russian Federation; the main provisions of the "Concept of the Russian language and literature" are considered in relation to teaching Russian as a foreign language. The author traces the history of the development of RFL as a science, explores the current problems of teaching Russian as a foreign language at the present stage, and proposes new approaches to the problem under consideration.

Keywords: Russian as a foreign language, Concept of the Russian language and literature, methodology, interdisciplinary approach, semiotics.

The problem of teaching Russian as a foreign language at the present stage is interdisciplinary in nature, which is due to the specifics of the educational system, characterized, on the one hand, by the desire for globalization, on the other hand, to preserve the national identity of a particular language.

Recently, due to increased attention to the processes and methods of communication, sign communication, the importance of semiotics, the science of signs, is increasing, the study of the effectiveness of which is important not only in theoretical terms, but also for a number of practical tasks [2]. The history of the sign goes through a difficult path in its development: from Aristotle, who believed that "words are signs of thought", Ch. S. Pierce, who wrote that "the whole universe is filled with symbols," to A.F. Losev, who recognized that "A symbol is an expanded sign." An important role in the development of Russian semiotics was played by the Tartu school of Yu. M. Lotman, who formulated the modern philosophy of the sign and symbol. Modern researchers note: "Semiotic studies ... bring closer to understanding not only the culture of individual peoples, but also their aesthetic universals and psychological constants of mankind [4]. At the same time, it should be taken into account that teaching Russian as a foreign language cannot and should not be reduced to the development of only reproductive skills of speech activity. Practice has shown that the time has come for new approaches to the implementation of this problem, which should be associated with the creation of a new generation of

educational and methodological literature that helps interactive learning, the use of new learning technologies. The actual problem of teaching Russian as a foreign language is the search for new means, forms, methods that are adequate to the goals of the development of the modern educational process. Stepanov Yu. S., speaking about the three-dimensional space of the language, noted: "Literally before our eyes, a single information world is being created, in which the world of fiction (in the form of intertext) and the world of science and technology (i.e., the infosphere) come together. "Intertext and infosphere are two key terms that characterize the new in semiotics, the semiotics of the second millennium" The teaching of Russian as a foreign language at the present stage of development of society must correspond to the new geopolitical, global socio-linguistic situation, new linguistic processes proper in the Russian language itself. Teaching Russian as a foreign language is intended to be creative and innovative and must be based on a truly scientific basis: it must be diverse, adequate to the cultural diversity of a person, satisfy the comprehensive needs of ethno-cultural, socio-professional, confessional groups. Very important for practical work are the conclusions of scientists that "learning must comply with the principles of the brain" [5], because the ability to process visual images is associated with the anatomical structure of the human brain. Therefore, it is no coincidence that an ethnomethodological approach to teaching Russian as a foreign language is especially in demand today.

In the modern educational system, it is necessary to create conditions that would serve as a real basis for the formation of a multicultural personality with a developed ethnic self-consciousness, capable of constructive cooperation with carriers of various ethnocultural values. Awareness of oneself as a representative of a certain ethnic group contributes to a deeper understanding of the cultural values of one's people, familiarization with world culture, the formation of a holistic perception, systemic thinking [6]. At the same time, it is important to consider multicultural education as the basis of a polylogue of cultures. The introduction of ethno-oriented control and measuring (assessment) means into the education system increases the efficiency of mastering Russian as a foreign language, subject to the personal, social (from socialization) significance of their content and implementation methodology. In order to maintain the motivation of foreign students in mastering Russian as a foreign language and optimizing learning, it is important to rely on the developed and stable aspects of ethnic psyche: a high level of mnemonic abilities (memorization, classification), developed intuition, visual perception channel, visual-motor memory channel, active use of analogy, contextual guessing. In the

process of speech activity, lexico-semantic errors are often encountered due to an incorrect or inaccurate understanding of the volume of words.

We are talking about effective methods that help foreigners to acquire language skills and speech competencies in the Russian language in a short time. To solve the tasks set, extraordinary, fundamentally new approaches to teaching this discipline are required.

The changed social and historical context of communication dictates a new modality for the presentation of educational material. In the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, it is important to take into account the national and cultural specifics of the language. Modern linguistic methodology recognizes the need to include a national-cultural component in language teaching as one of the most important ways of translating national culture. Linguists from different countries and eras were looking for that rational grain that would make the language attractive for knowledge and study.

Teacher's techniques, methods, forms of work in teaching any subject set, that is, the teacher's art, skill.

Opportunities to achieve the maximum result of the educational process and science that studies tools, that is, the theory of teaching any subject. Methodology as a future science, to students of Russian as a foreign language will be the object of our attention as a teaching theory. Methodical science in order to understand it and highlight the positive experience born of practice. The development of science and practice occurs in full interaction will be known that theory is always enriched by practice.

Certain conditions are needed to make the speech:

- 1) the presence of a speech situation that motivates to speak;
- 2) availability of knowledge (grammatical and lexical) to express one's thoughts;
- 3) presence of attitude to the subject of speech;
- 4) the existence of the purpose of conveying one's thoughts.

Communication can be different - individual, group and public.

Group communication differs from individual communication not only by the number of communication partners, rather, it differs primarily from itself. Public communication (meetings, rallies, debates, conferences) usually predetermines the communicative roles of the participants: their some act as speakers, others as listeners.

The main stages of working on speech material in teaching speech:

1. The stage of skill formation, which consists of two sub-stages: formation of lexical skills and formation of grammatical skills. Building skills can be called pre-textual, however the material itself is taken from the text.

2. Stage of improvement of skills. Here we are working on an educational text goes, that is. based on the material fully mastered in the first stage text. This step can be called text.

3. The stage of development of speech skills is also the stage after the text it does not cause less difficulty.

Methodology of Russian language learning is a cross-cultural assessment having principles, pedagogical in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language aimed at forming a communicative multilingual person in contact. That is why in this study, the formation of each skill methodological approaches used for learning pronunciation is a practical part of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

As a result, phonetic skills, if the pronunciation is sufficiently accurate can be considered formed. To the level of listening and speaking skills requirements depend on the objectives and conditions of training, in some cases they are limited to defining acceptable pronunciation

At the initial stage, a number of tasks are distinguished in the teaching of vocabulary:

1) with a minimum vocabulary for the student's daily speech and learning activities

providing, therefore, a vocabulary combined with relevant topics is selected and include: "Reading", "My Day", "My Room", "Shop", "Clothes-yesterday";

2) the core of the future user's dictionary is Russian, a non-native language create as;

3) the lexical basis of formation of speech skills and qualifications provide;

4) creating a lexical base of grammar teaching.

Basic training lexical exercises:

a) gap filling exercises (required words are taken from memory);

b) question-and-answer exercises (words developed in the answer are used);

c) exercises for making sentences with the participation of new words;

d) speech patterns by using new words as adverbs and cases stretching exercises;

e) translation exercises into the target language;

f) exercises for matching (form a phrase from two columns);

- g) exercises for synonymy, thematic grouping;
- i) exercises to recognize words in context [7].

Among the exercises of the receptive type, an important place is the analysis of words and context by making a linguistic assumption about the meaning of a new word in the reader exercises aimed at development. Among the urgent problems of teaching Russian as a foreign language, one can rightfully consider the appeal to fiction, which reflects the philosophy of the Russian language, history, culture, traditions, and customs of the Russian people to the greatest extent. In the modern methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, literary texts are considered as a means that forms an individual, allowing one to penetrate into the diversity of linguistic forms, to comprehend the richness of the language being studied. Working with the text of fiction contributes to a high level of knowledge of the language and its understanding as a cultural code, the creation of the image of Russia that will most contribute to the formation of positive motivation in the study of Russian literature and prepare them for an adequate perception of life values and values based on knowledge of national cultural stereotypes. landmarks. Working with a literary text makes it possible to identify the linguistic, linguo-stylistic, linguo-culturological features of the text that form the "image of the Russian literary text", to determine the "text concept". The adaptation of foreigners to teaching the Russian language is a multi-level, dynamic process that has its own structure and flow characteristics associated with a certain restructuring of the personality as part of inclusion in new social roles.

In this, interactive teaching technologies play an important role, which include various methodological techniques of a synergistic nature, as well as the organic inclusion of fiction texts in the RFL teaching system using their graphic-symbolic analysis.

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